

An efficient and reusable non-ionic surfactant-catalysed synthesis of bis-coumarin derivatives in aqueous media[†]

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Abstract : A green and expedient synthetic method has been developed for the facile synthesis of bis-coumarin derivatives in the presence of the non-ionic surfactant Triton X-100 in an aqueous medium at room temperature with almost 100% yields. Aldehyde and 4-hydroxycoumarin are the only starting materials for the one-pot synthesis of bis-coumarin derivatives and the non-ionic surfactant catalyst can be recovered very easily. We also observed that during the reaction there was the formation of micelles, or micelle-like colloidal aggregates, from the non-ionic surfactant and the reaction mixture in water, measured by dynamic light scattering and visualized through optical microscope.

Keywords : Bis-coumarin derivatives, Triton X-100, aqueous media.

Introduction

Green chemistry can be renowned as revolutionary research, which widely reports intrinsic atom-economy, energy savings, waste reduction, easy work-ups and the avoidance of hazardous chemicals¹. In organic chemistry, the motivation has been made on the search for alternate chemical pathways to achieve the desired chemical conversions with minimal exposure of toxic wastes to environment². The most attractive alternative to organic solvents is water which has an apparent increasing popularity due to being cheap and readily available and relevant character³.

In addition, reactions in aqueous media illustrate distinctive reactivities and unique selectivities that are not usually observed in organic media⁴. However, organic reactions in water are often limited in scope due to the poor solubility of the organic compounds. A possible new way to improve the solubility of substrates is the use of surface-active compounds that can form micelles. Under ambient conditions, surfactant molecules can aggregate in an aqueous phase to form micelles with a hydrophobic core and a hydrophilic corona. Non-ionic surfactants have

the tendency to adsorb at interfaces and to form micelles; otherwise, their critical micelle concentration (CMC) is similar to the ionic surfactants. However, the benefit of non-ionic surfactants (e.g. Triton X-100) is the absence of the electrical double layer, as formed by the ionic surfactants. Hence, we planned to utilize these properties of non-ionic surfactant for our present study.

In recent years, multicomponent reactions (MCRs), involving three or more reactants in one-pot, have been used to synthesize structurally diverse bioactive heterocyclic compounds⁵. The advantages of multicomponent reactions are high atom-economy, structural diversity, operational simplicity and lack of waste products in a multi-step reaction.

Coumarins are an important class of bio-active organic compounds generally used as additives to food, in cosmetics and as optical brightening agents⁶. In addition, dicoumarol is a member of an important class of naturally occurring coumarin derivatives (Fig. 1). It is an anticoagulant and also functions as a vitamin K antagonist and displays anticancer activities⁷.

[†]In honour of Professor Sunil Kumar Talapatra on the occasion of his 80th birthday.

Fig. 1. Biologically active bis-coumarin derivatives.

A variety of methods have been materialized to achieve the synthesis of this dicoumarol. Despite some progress, most of the methods⁸⁻¹² suffer from a number of disadvantages, like using organic solvents, acidic reaction conditions, high reaction temperatures and low catalytic efficiencies. Surprisingly, very little is known about the surfactant-catalyzed synthesis of bis-coumarin derivatives.

In continuation of our ongoing research involving water as a solvent and surfactant as the key catalyst in organic transformation¹³, we wish to report herein, a highly efficient procedure for the preparation of bis-coumarin derivatives via a one-pot, three-component reaction using the non-ionic surfactant Triton X-100 in aqueous media at room temperature with almost 100% yields (Scheme 1). The catalyst has been recycled several times with no substantial loss in activity.

temperature in the presence of water and ethanol as the solvents, without any catalyst. However, even after 24 h, the reactions failed to afford any product (Table 1, entries 1 and 2). The reactions were also restrained by using the anionic surfactant SDS (sodium dodecyl sulphate) as the catalyst (Table 1, entry 3). The use of a cationic surfactant CTAB (cetyl trimethylammonium bromide) as a catalyst in aqueous media provided a slight higher yield than the anionic surfactant (Table 1, entry 4) of the desired product. We then applied a non-ionic surfactant, Triton X-100 (10 mol%) as the catalyst in water. Eventually we achieved satisfaction because the reaction proceeded well, affording the desired product in a 98% yield with in 6 h (Table 1, entry 5). Triton X-100 played an amazing catalytic role in this particular MCR in comparison to the other surfactants applied, which can be attrib-

Scheme 1. Synthesis of bis-coumarin derivatives.

Results and discussion

In order to optimize the reaction conditions and identify the best surfactant catalysts, the reaction was studied by employing surfactant catalysts with solvents, as well as under solvent-free conditions, with the hope of maximizing the product yield in short reaction times (Table 1). In our initial studies, we used 3-nitrobenzaldehyde **1** (1.0 mmol) and 4-hydroxycoumarin **2** (1.0 mmol) as model substrates (Scheme 1) and these were stirred at room

uted to its high solubilizing capacity related to its hydrophobic character; in addition, the surfactant properties of Triton X-100 improve the reaction kinetics by increasing the interfacial area and also the aggregation number of the micelles. An increase in the aggregation number results in an increase in the surface charge of the micellar units, which can subsequently create ambient conditions which optimize the reaction purity, yield and speed for the reaction to move forward.

Table 1. Screening of catalyst and solvents and reaction conditions^a

Entry	Catalysts	Solvents	Conditions	Time (h)	Yields ^b (%)
1	-	H ₂ O	RT	24	<i>c</i>
2	-	EtOH	RT	24	<i>c</i>
3	SDS (10 mol%)	H ₂ O	RT	24	24
4	CTAB (10 mol%)	H ₂ O	RT	24	41
5	Triton X-100 (10 mol%)	H ₂ O	RT	6	98
6	Triton X-100 (15 mol%)	H ₂ O	RT	6	88
7	Triton X-100 (5 mol%)	H ₂ O	RT	6	85
8	Triton X-100 (10 mol%)	H ₂ O	Reflux	6	69
9	Triton X-100 (10 mol%)	EtOH	RT	6	66
10	Triton X-100 (10 mol%)	CHCl ₃	RT	6	59
11	Triton X-100 (10 mol%)	CH ₃ CN	RT	6	44
12	Triton X-100 (10 mol%)	-	RT	6	32

^aAll reactions were carried out with *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde (1 mmol), 4-hydroxycoumarin (2 mmol). ^bYield of isolated product. ^cReaction failed to provide any product.

Table 2. Substrate scope for the synthesis of bis-coumarin derivatives^a

Entry	R	Time (h)	Product	Yield ^b (%)
1	 3a	97		
2	 3b	98		
3	 3c	94		
4	 3d	94		
5	 3e	98		
6	 3f	97		
7	 3g	95		
8	 3h	97		

Evaluating Triton X-100 as the right choice of catalyst for the experiment, we then concentrated our attention on designing and also generalizing the promising conditions for the reaction. We firstly attempted some screening tests with Triton X-100. The quantity of the catalyst had a large effect on the formation of the desired product. The use of 15 mol% Triton X-100 diminished the quantity of the yield, whereas the yield of the product was much decreased when we used 5 mol% Triton X-100 (Table 1, entries 6 and 7). The yields of the desired product also decreased when Triton X-100 was refluxed with water (Table 1, entry 8). Water showed superiority to the other solvents tested [ethanol (Table 1, entry 9), chloroform (Table 1, entry 10) and acetonitrile (Table 1, entry 11)], while under the solvent-free conditions (Table 1, entry 12) at room temperature, Triton X-100 failed to provide satisfactory outputs. Therefore, water was chosen as the solvent for this reaction as the maximum yield (98%) was obtained under aqueous conditions. Hence, these optimized conditions were followed for all experiments.

To test the generality of this reaction, a series of aromatic and heteroaromatic aldehydes were subjected to achieve the corresponding dicoumarol in the optimal reaction conditions (Table 2). The reactions proceeded smoothly and provided excellent yields and tolerated unsubstituted benzaldehydes, and both electron-withdraw-

Table-2 (contd.)

9		96		
			3i	
10		94		
			3j	
11		97		
			3k	
12		96		
			3l	

^aAldehyde (1 mmol) and 4-hydroxycoumarin (2 mmol) were stirred in 5 mL water in the presence of 10 mol% Triton X-100. ^bIsolated yield of the pure product.

ing and electron-donating *para*-substituted benzaldehydes at room temperature.

The reusability of the catalyst was studied through the condensation of 3-nitrobenzaldehyde and 4-hydroxycoumarin. Upon completion of the reaction, the product was filtered and washed with water and the unused starting materials were extracted using diethyl ether and the separated micellar media were reused for the next cycle. The recycling could be followed five consecutive times with almost unaltered catalytic activity (recovery amount 94% and yield 92%, after the 5th run). The reactions were consistently carried out at the 1 mmol scale and no change of product yield was observed when scaled up to the 10 mmol scales at room temperature. The catalytic effect of micellar Triton X-100 in this reaction can be explained as follows : in the micellar solution aldehyde and 4-hydroxycoumarin which being hydrophobic, are forced inside the hydrophobic core of the micelles, thus allowing the reaction to take place more easily.

It is pertinent to mention that the addition of Triton X-100 in the reaction flask converted the initially floating reaction mass into a homogeneous mixture, which on stirring became a white turbid emulsion. This observation implies that there was formation of micelles or micelle-like colloidal aggregates. The average sizes of the colloidal particles formed from Triton X-100 and the reaction mixture in water were measured by dynamic light scattering and appeared to be about 200 nm in diameter (Fig. 2a). Formation of emulsion droplets in the present reaction system was also confirmed by optical microscopy (Fig. 2b).

a

b

Fig. 2. (a) DLS study of the reaction media showing formation of aggregates. (b) Optical microscopic image showing nanovesicles in the reaction media.

The formation of the desired product indicates that surfactants played an important role to stabilize the Knoevenagel intermediate (I) which is formed by aldehyde **1** and a 4-hydroxycoumarin **2** unit. Subsequent nu-

Scheme 2. Micelle-promoted reaction pathway for the formation of bis-coumarin.

cleophilic addition of 4-hydroxycoumarin results in the formation of only one product (3). This Knoevenagel product formation is the most attractive feature of our reaction in aqueous medium. The water molecules generated by Knoevenagel formation are expelled from the micelle due to hydrophobic nature of their interior (Scheme 2).

Conclusions

In summary, a new and easy to perform synthetic method in aqueous media using Triton X-100 as the surfactant catalyst (10 mol%) has been successfully developed for the facile synthesis of bis-coumarin derivatives. The operational simplicity and excellent yields of the products at room temperature are the main advantages of this method and furthermore, this procedure is very cheap, safe and environmentally benign, which makes this methodology a world-wide concern.

Experimental

General procedure for the preparation of bis-coumarin derivatives (3a-3l) :

The aldehyde (1) (1 mmol) and 4-hydroxycoumarin (2) (2 mmol) were added to a solution of Triton X-100 (10 mol%) in H₂O (3 mL), and the mixture was stirred at room temperature. The resulting clear solution, that gradually became turbid, was allowed to stir for the stipulated time mentioned in Table 2. After completion of the reaction (indicated by TLC), the free-flowing solid mass was filtered and washed with water (20 ml) to afford the desired products (3) as pale yellow solid. The products thus obtained were recrystallized from ethanol to give pure compounds as white or pale yellow crystals. All compounds were well characterized by ¹H, ¹³C NMR and FTIR analysis.

3,3'-(Phenylmethylene)bis-(4-hydroxy-2H-chromen-2-one) (3a) : 97% (0.399 g) white solid; m.p. 230 °C; IR

(KBr) : 3080, 1675, 1567 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 6.21 (1H, s), 7.08–7.31 (11H, m), 7.51 (2H, t, J 7.8 Hz), 7.9 (2H, d, J 7.5 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (75.5 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 35.6, 104.2, 116.0, 116.2, 123.7, 124.2, 126.1, 128.05, 128.6, 132.5, 136.0, 151.9, 167.2, 166.5.

3,3'-((3-Nitrophenyl)methylene)bis(4-hydroxy-2H-chromen-2-one) (**3b**) : 98% (0.447 g) white solid; m.p. 145 $^\circ\text{C}$; IR (KBr) : 3059, 1667, 1610, 1545, 1340 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 6.41 (1H, s), 6.72–7.94 (12H, m), 11.24 (2H, br s); ^{13}C NMR (75.5 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 33.7, 102.5, 115.8, 116.4, 119.2, 123.9, 124.7, 126.6, 129.6, 131.54, 131.8, 152.1, 168.02, 172.4.

3,3'-((4-Methoxyphenyl)methylene)bis(4-hydroxy-2H-chromen-2-one) (**3c**) : 94% (0.415 g) pale yellow solid; m.p. 214 $^\circ\text{C}$; IR (KBr) : 3445, 1668, 1602 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 3.61 (3H, s), 6.20 (1H, s), 6.70 (2H, d, J 6 Hz), 6.96 (2H, d, J 6 Hz), 7.21–7.28 (4H, m), 7.48–7.82 (4H, m); ^{13}C NMR (75.5 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 33.7, 102.5, 115.8, 116.4, 119.2, 123.9, 124.7, 126.6, 129.6, 131.54, 131.8, 152.1, 168.0, 172.4.

3,3'-((2-Hydroxyphenyl)methylene)bis(4-hydroxy-2H-chromen-2-one) (**3d**) : 94% (0.402 g) pale yellow solid; m.p. 197 $^\circ\text{C}$; IR (KBr) : 3335, 1712, 1672 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 5.71 (1H, s), 6.88–8.31 (12H, m), 10.68 (1H, s); ^{13}C NMR (75.5 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 23.5, 108.6, 111.1, 111.3, 111.9, 113.3, 114.2, 117.1, 117.5, 118.8, 119.4, 119.7, 120.2, 123.2, 124.6, 127.0, 128.2, 130.2, 137.7, 144.0, 146.8, 153.5, 155.3.

3,3'-((4-Bromophenyl)methylene)bis(4-hydroxy-2H-chromen-2-one) (**3e**) : 98% (0.480 g) white solid; m.p. 251 $^\circ\text{C}$; IR (KBr) : 3034, 1672, 1602, 756 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 6.29 (1H, s), 7.09–7.90 (12H, m); ^{13}C NMR (75.5 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 35.8, 91.0, 103.8, 115.9, 116.4, 118.1, 118.5, 123.2, 129.2, 130.8, 131.9, 132.7, 139.9, 152.3, 164.7, 165.6.

3,3'-((Thiophen-2-yl)methylene)bis(4-hydroxy-2H-chromen-2-one) (**3f**) : 97% (0.405 g) light green solid; m.p. 212 $^\circ\text{C}$; IR (KBr) : 3074, 1660, 1612 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 6.39 (1H, s), 6.57 (1H, s), 6.78 (1H, s), 7.13–7.53 (8H, m), 7.83 (2H, d, J 7.6 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (75.5 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 32.9, 103.7, 115.5, 119.9, 122.6, 122.9, 124.2, 126.1, 131.1, 148.1, 152.5, 164.1, 167.9.

3,3'-((Pyridin-2-yl)methylene)bis(4-hydroxy-2H-chromen-2-one) (**3g**) : 95% (0.390 g) pale yellow solid; m.p. 252 $^\circ\text{C}$; IR (KBr) : 3174, 3133, 1688, 1592 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 6.44 (1H, s), 7.15–7.82 (10H, m), 8.36 (1H, t, J 7.5 Hz), 8.54 (1H, d, J 5.1 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (75.5 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 37.0, 100.9, 116.3, 119.6, 123.7, 124.7, 126.3, 132.3, 142.2, 146.7, 153.2, 158.0, 164.3, 168.9.

3,3'-((2-Chlorophenyl)methylene)bis(4-hydroxy-2H-chromen-2-one) (**3h**) : 97% (0.432 g) white solid; m.p. 198 $^\circ\text{C}$; IR (KBr) : 3099, 1675, 766 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 6.19 (1H, s), 7.18–7.92 (12H, m); ^{13}C NMR (75.5 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 36.7, 104.5, 116.4, 116.7, 118.2, 123.6, 124.1, 126.8, 127.9, 130.1, 132.7, 139.7, 152.6, 160.8, 164.9, 190.2.

3,3'-((4-Fluorophenyl)methylene)bis(4-hydroxy-2H-chromen-2-one) (**3i**) : 96% (0.412 g) white solid; m.p. 192 $^\circ\text{C}$; IR (KBr) : 3079, 1666, 761 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 6.29 (1H, s), 6.97–7.88 (12H, m); ^{13}C NMR (75.5 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 35.9, 104.5, 114.9, 115.2, 116.4, 118.5, 124.1, 124.4, 128.9, 129.0, 132.3, 136.6, 152.7, 159.3, 162.5, 165.2, 165.9.

(E)-3,3'-((3-Phenylprop-2-ene-1,1-diyl)bis(4-hydroxy-2H-chromen-2-one) (**3j**) : 94% (0.411 g) white solid; m.p. 206 $^\circ\text{C}$; IR (KBr) : 3027, 1671, 1618, 1567, 1352 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 5.51 (1H, s), 6.22–6.25 (1H, m), 6.65–6.73 (2H, m), 7.00–7.32 (8H, m), 7.36–7.55 (5H, m); ^{13}C NMR (75.5 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 35.7, 39.9, 69.0, 91.9, 116.8, 123.6, 124.5, 127.2, 128.3, 129.9, 131.8, 133.2, 156.5.

3,3'-((2,3-Dichlorophenyl)methylene)bis(4-hydroxy-2H-chromen-2-one) (**3k**) : 97% (0.465 g) white solid; m.p. 223 $^\circ\text{C}$; IR (KBr) : 3320, 1661, 1566, 768 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 6.16 (1H, s), 7.27–7.87 (11H, m); ^{13}C NMR (75.5 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 37.4, 103.5, 115.8, 118.7, 123.4, 124.0, 127.2, 128.0, 129.1, 130.6, 131.7, 142.8, 152.4, 163.6, 166.1.

3,3'-((p-Tolyl)methylene)bis(4-hydroxy-2H-chromen-2-one) (**3l**) : 96% (0.407 g) white solid; m.p. 223 $^\circ\text{C}$; IR (KBr) : 3320, 1661, 1566, 768 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 6.31 (1H, s), 7.02 (4H, s), 7.32–7.91 (8H, m); ^{13}C NMR (75.5 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 36.4, 103.8, 115.9, 117.7, 123.0, 125.0, 127.2, 128.7, 129.6, 131.7, 137.4, 144.8, 153.4, 156.5, 165.5.

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